

Dynamic modeling and simulation of a solar-assisted multi-effect distillation plant

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Abstract

This paper presents a dynamic model of a solar-assisted multi-effect distillation (MED) plant, carrying on with the previous work "Dynamic modeling and performance of the first cell of a multi-effect distillation plant"[1]. The dynamic model has been designed according to the experience with an experimental solar thermal desalination system erected at CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA). The mathematical formulation based on physical principles describes the main heat and mass transfer phenomena in this kind of facilities. The model was implemented using the equation-based object-oriented Modelica modeling language. Based on a modular and hierarchical modeling, different specific-phenomenon submodels have been developed. They have been interconnected between them, thus making a three levels deep hierarchy. All the submodels have been calibrated and validated with experimental data. The numerical predictions show a good agreement with measured data.

Keywords: solar desalination, falling film evaporation and condensation, object-oriented modeling, Modelica

1. Introduction

Water is an essential part of life. The lack of fresh water in areas with high water-stress is one of the most important problems which researchers face. Three-fourths part of The Earth surface is covered by water, but the 97% is salt water. Seawater desalination is one of the possible solutions for coastal regions, but, it requires significant quantities of energy in order to achieve separation of salt from seawater. Coupling desalination plants with renewable energies is a way to reduce the environmental pollution of this process. Solar energy is one of the most promising alternatives since it is usual to find high insolation levels in high water-stress areas [2].

Reverse osmosis (RO), multi-stage flash (MSF) and MED account for more than 94% of the global desalination capacity [3]. Among them, MSF and MED technologies can be coupled with solar thermal systems because most of the energy consumption is thermal energy. Both technologies allow to be coupled in two separated devices, the solar collector and the distiller. MED technology carries on being preferred in most of the large scale solar thermal plants due to its low top brine temperature (TBT), typically less than 80°C, and its low specific energy consumption requirements [4].

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4 The collector is a device which captures the solar radiation and transfers its heat to a fluid. In solar-
5 assisted MED plants, the working fluid is commonly water or synthetic oil and it is usually stored in a
6 thermal storage system [5]. The solar collector or the storage system can be directly connected to the
7 MED unit or indirectly by means of a heat exchanger.
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9 There are many kinds of MED plants, but in all of them, the distillation process is similar. The plant
10 is made up of a series of hermetic elements, called effects, connected between them. At each one, a series
11 of simultaneous evaporation/condensation processes take place in a decreasing sequence of pressures and
12 temperatures. At the first effect, the one with the highest pressure, an external heat source drives the first
13 boiling of the seawater that flows inside. The steam generated within the effect is used as the heat source
14 of the next effect, so, while on one hand, the incoming steam is condensing, on the other, the seawater is
15 boiling, and thus producing additional steam. This process is repeated in each effect [3].
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17 The process model and simulation can provide insight about the physical phenomena and give detailed
18 information about the performance that may be useful in order to improve the efficiency of the plant
19 over a wide range of operating conditions without experimentation in the real plant. Several steady-
20 state models have been published covering a wide variety of plant configurations. Some of the most
21 recent contributions in this area have been done by Kouhikamali who studied the influence of different
22 configurations of feed water preheating [6], Joo and Kwak who increased the mechanical efficiency and
23 economical profit of a MED system [7] or Palenzuela et al. who evaluated different cooling technologies
24 of concentrated solar power plants and their combination with desalination processes (RO and MED) [8].
25 The contributions made by El-Nashar [9, 10] and Palenzuela et al. [11] deserve special attention because
26 they validated their respective models with experimental data.
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28 The literature related to dynamic modeling is scarce. However, the interest for this kind of modeling
29 has grown recently. Kishore et al. [12] presented a work-in-progress simulator for the steady state and the
30 dynamics of a multi-effect distillation mechanical vapour compression (MED-VC) desalination system,
31 showing a dynamic simulation of a single effect. Roca et al. [13] developed a dynamic model of a
32 multi-effect distillation plant based on the heat transfer correlations presented in [14]. This model is an
33 improved version of a previous one in which the heat transfer coefficients were considered constants [15].
34 It was developed with the object-oriented Modelica language and its main purpose was the prediction
35 of the thermal dynamics of the heater and the distillate production rate. Kim et al. [16] presented a
36 simulation model for predicting transient behavior of a solar-assisted MED plant. The model, which was
37 focused on the long-term thermal and performance analysis, includes an evacuated-tube collector, a plate
38 heat exchanger, storage tanks and a MED plant. This model has been used by Thu et al. [17] in the study
39 of a suitable configuration for a hybridization between adsorption desalination (AD) and MED processes.
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41 The present paper carries on the work started in [1] where the focus was on the modeling of the first ef-
42 fect of a solar-assisted MED plant. Using an object-oriented modeling methodology, the model presented
43 was divided into submodels that encapsulated and covered the dynamics of each one of the subprocesses
44 that take place in the system. Reusing part of this work and following with this modeling methodology,
45 a new dynamic model of a MED plant has been developed in order to study its performance in different
46 scenarios and design operating strategies to improve its efficiency. This non-linear first principles model
47 has been implemented with the object-oriented Modelica language. The model uses as inputs the natural
48 inputs of the system, i.e., the hot water flow, the inlet seawater flow and the ambient temperature. The
49 model is based on the AQUASOL experimental solar desalination system [18] and it has been calibrated
50 and validated with experimental data. The model predicts the transient thermal behavior of each effect
51 and its low computational effort allows fast simulation for control purposes.
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2. Description of the plant

In 1987, a MED unit manufactured by ENTROPIE was erected at CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería with the aim of testing and developing the solar thermal MED process. Since then, the original experimental solar desalination system has been undergone several changes until becoming a 24-h operation hybrid solar-gas desalination system (v. Fig. 1) that tries to meet at the same time the requirements of low-cost, high efficiency and zero liquid discharge [18]. The current system is flexible regarding the energy supply of the MED plant, it can be thermal-fed by a compound parabolic collector (CPC) solar field, by a propane gas boiler by means of a double effect absorption heat pump (DEAHP) or in a hybrid mode by both. The DEAHP is coupled with the last effect of the MED plant recovering part of its low-temperature energy. This energy is injected to the MED plant directly or through the tanks indirectly at high temperature [19].

The distillation unit is a forward-feed vertically stacked MED plant with 14 cells (v. Fig. 2). In 2005 under the framework of the AQUASOL project, the original first effect was replaced with a new one able to work with hot water coming either from the thermal storage tanks or from the DEAHP. The hot water inlet temperature can vary between 57-75 °C, exhibiting low deviations in the overall performance ratio [20]. This temperature can be controlled with a three-way valve placed between the hot tank and the MED plant. The inlet flow rate can range between 7-12 L/s.

Besides the first and the last cells, the remaining cells are identical. Every cell is composed of an effect and a preheater, two horizontal tube bundles, where, over the first one, seawater evaporation is produced and, over the second one, part of the vapor is condensed. Fig. 3 shows a schematic cross section of a cell. The first effect is a square-pitch bundle and hot water flows inside the tubes crossing the evaporator four times in a highly turbulent flow [1]. The last cell preheater, also called condenser, is much bigger than the other preheaters.

A flow diagram of the plant is depicted in Fig. 4. A great amount of seawater is pumped to the condenser placed next to the 14th effect which is used to condense the vapor generated in such effect. Seawater is also used for preserving the pressure inside, however, there is not an specific control system for this purpose. Using a three way valve, part of this seawater is rejected and the remaining part is used to feed the plant. The feed seawater flow rate, that can vary between 6-8 m³/h, is preheated while flows through every cell, and finally, it is spilt inside the plant in the 1st cell. Here, seawater is sprayed over the effect where hot water flows inside the tubes transferring heat. When the spray reaches the first row of the tube bundle, a thin film of seawater is formed over each tube surface. The seawater in the film flows downward due to the gravitational force, falling over all the column tubes. Part of seawater evaporates in the effect and the remaining part, with higher salt concentration, falls over the next effect. The vapor produced at the effect flows to the preheater located next to it. A wire mesh demister prevents brine droplets from reaching the preheater tube bundle. When condensation is produced over the tube surface, a thin film of water is formed. This film slides down due to the gravitational force and it falls over all the column tubes increasing their thickness as more vapor condenses on the film. Seawater flows inside the tubes, acquiring heat from the condensation. The distillate and the vapor, which has not condensed, flow to inside the horizontal tube bundle of the next effect. This mixture is used to heat the high concentrated seawater coming from the 1st effect where this process is repeated.

The decreasing pressure arrangement provides an efficient heat transfer between the vapor-distillate mixture and the seawater coming from the previous effect because the difference between the saturation temperatures of seawater and vapor at same pressure is not large enough. When seawater enters to the effect, the pressure drop between effects produces flash evaporation which in turn decreases the

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4 seawater temperature before covering the surface of the tubes. For this reason, seawater is always at
5 lower temperature than the water which flows inside the tubes.
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7 The vapor condensed at each effect, each preheater and the distillate produced at the final condenser
8 make up the total distillate production of the plant. Part of sensible heat of the distillate is recovered by
9 the plant when flows inside the tube bundle of the effects. With the purpose of improving the process
10 at PSA-MED plant, the distillate accumulated in one preheater is added to the distillate produced in the
11 effect and flow to the next effect with the exception of the 4th, 7th, 13th and 14th cells as it is shown in
12 Fig. 4. In the 4th cell the distillate is divided, one part flows to the 7th cell and the remaining part flows
13 to the 10th cell where it is mixed with the extraction of the 7th cell. This mixture flows to the 10th and
14 13th cells. The distillate accumulated in the 10th cell is mixed with the extracted from the 7th cell and
15 divided again, one part flows to 13th cell and the remaining together with the distillate from the 13th and
16 14th cells flows to the condenser where part is evaporated by a flash process.
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19 The salt water for the desalination plant is obtained by brackish water wells from Tabernas Dessert
20 whose salinity is 0.3326%. The MED plant is operated in a close circuit. Two pools are used to store
21 all the seawater: a small pool is used to mix the distillate and the brine rejected and a bigger one for the
22 supply of the plant. The cooling seawater is spilt into the big pool and part of the heat released by the
23 condenser could increase its temperature during a experiment. To avoid that, a dry cooler is switched on,
24 however sometimes it is insufficient [11]. Therefore, it is difficult to obtain a long-steady state in all its
25 variables even though the MED plant has control mechanisms at its inputs.
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28 The MED plant has a vacuum system in order to remove the air and the non-condensable gases
29 generated during the desalination process. It consists in two hydro-ejectors which are connected to the
30 2nd and 7th effects and to the final condenser. This system removes the gases at the beginning of the
31 experiment, being water vapor the only gas inside the effects. The hydro-ejectors are within a closed
32 circuit with a tank and an electric pump that drives seawater through the ejectors at a pressure of 3 bar
33 [11].
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36 The current design specifications of the MED plant are shown in Table 1 [11]. All the tube bundles
37 are made of 90-10 Cu-Ni with a 14 mm of outside diameter. The heat transfer areas are:
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- 39 • 1st effect: 24.26 m²
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- 41 • 2nd-14th effect: 26.28 m²
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- 43 • Preheater: 5 m²
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- 45 • Condenser: 18.3 m²
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49 3. Subsystem Modeling

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51 In §1, it is mentioned that modeling and simulation is a powerful methodology to improve the ef-
52 ficiency of processes. This is because simulations can predict the plant behavior over different design
53 operating conditions. Due to the complexity of this process, it is important to identify and model each
54 one of the subprocesses in order to cover all the dynamics with enough detail. The object-oriented mod-
55 eling methodology allows to encapsulate each one of these subprocesses into submodels. The general
56 model is composed of these submodels.
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58 The model has been implemented with the non-proprietary Modelica language [21]. This modeling
59 language allows to formulate the problems in an acausal way, being well suited for representing physical
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4 systems. Moreover, Modelica is an object-oriented language, therefore, each component diagram can be
5 encapsulated in a class and hierarchical structures can be created.
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7 Three levels are enough to develop the model of the MED plant. The low level cover each subpro-
8 cess of heat and mass transfer of the system, the medium level assembles subsystems dealing with its
9 usefulness, and the high level composes the complete model of the plant.
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11 In computational fluid dynamics, the procedure to calculate the thermodynamic properties has a great
12 influence on the error and on the computational time [22]. There are several problems related with
13 dynamic models that are directly caused by the computation scheme applied to them. With respect to
14 the models described in this section, the industrial formulation for thermodynamic properties of water
15 and steam [23] has been used in the models with water and vapor. For the models with seawater, the
16 properties has been calculated with the formulation proposed by Sharqawy et al. [24] and the inverse
17 functions presented in [1].
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19 The details of all variables used in this section are described in the nomenclature.
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21 3.1. Low level

22 3.1.1. Falling film condenser

23 Mostly, condensation happens over surfaces whose temperature is lower than the saturation temper-
24 ature. At falling film condensers, like the preheaters of PSA-MED plant, when condensation appears a
25 thin film of water grows over each tube surface. This film slides down under gravitational force and falls
26 over all the column of tubes increasing their thickness because more vapor condenses over the film. The
27 film thickness determines the mass and heat flow rates.
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29 Based on the model presented in [1], the model showed in Fig. 5(a) determines, by an algebraic
30 procedure, the distillate production using only one control volume (CV). The heat transfer between the
31 tube and the condensate is calculated according to the Nusselt film condensation theory and the Newton's
32 law of viscosity [25]. An average temperature of the film between vapor saturation temperature at the
33 vapor-film interface and the tube temperature at the surface is assumed. Also, it is considered that the
34 film drains smoothly over the tube below. With these assumptions, the average heat transfer coefficient
35 can be calculated as follows [26]:
36

$$37 \bar{\alpha}_c = 0.729 \left(\frac{\rho_c(\rho_c - \rho_{c,sv})gk_c^3 L_c^*}{2\mu_c(T_{c,sl} - T_{c,w})r_c N_{c,row}} \right)^{1/4}, \quad (1)$$

38 where the modified latent heat of vaporization is defined as:
39

$$40 L_c^* = L_c + 0.68C_{p,c}(T_{c,sl} + T_{c,w}). \quad (2)$$

41 The total condensation rate by the tube bundle is determined by the Newton's law of cooling:
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$$43 \dot{m}_{c,cond} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{c,w}}{L_c^*} = \frac{\max(0, N_{c,col} N_{c,row} \bar{\alpha}_c A_{c,w} (T_{c,sl} - T_{c,w}))}{L_c^*}. \quad (3)$$

44 The max function guarantees a condensation rate only when the wall temperature is lower than the satu-
45 ration temperature.
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3.1.2. Horizontal tube bundle condenser

Inside the horizontal tube bundle of each effect a vapor-distillate mixture coming from the previous effect releases its latent heat and part of its sensible heat in order to evaporate the seawater that flows over the outer surface. The decreasing pressure arrangement of the effects guarantees that the tube temperature is lower than the saturation temperature of the incoming vapor. When the vapor condenses at the inner surface of the tube, a thin film of water grows covering this surface. The liquid film drains downwards due to the gravitational force and it becomes more bulky at the bottom of the tube than at the top. A stratified liquid layer is formed at the bottom of the tube and flows axially. While the distillate crosses the tube, it transfers part of its sensible heat since the tube temperature is lower than the temperature of the distillate. A detailed analysis of condensation inside tubes is complicated because factors like the vapor velocity and the rate of liquid accumulation on the walls of the tubes strongly influence the process.

As the model of the falling film condenser §3.1.1, the model of the horizontal tube condenser (v. Fig. 5(b)) assumes an average heat transfer coefficient. If the heat transfer at the bottom of the tube is negligible compared to the upper portion of the tube, and the void fraction (and hence the interfacial area) does not vary significantly along the tube, Chato [27] recommends this expression:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{bc} = 0.555 \left(\frac{\rho_{bc}(\rho_{bc} - \rho_{bc,sv})gk_{bc}^3 I_c^*}{2\mu_{bc}(T_{bc,sl} - T_{bc,w})r_{bc}N_{bc,row}} \right)^{1/4}. \quad (4)$$

Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 are used to obtain the total condensation rate over the tube bundle. The condensate has an average temperature between the vapor saturation temperature and the tube temperature.

During the normal operation of the plant, it has been observed that the vapor of one effect never reaches the next effect crossing the condenser, therefore, the model avoid this situation assuming only liquid as output. The dynamics of the accumulation of liquid in the condenser are neglected. The mass balance is:

$$0 = \dot{m}_{bc,in} - \dot{m}_{bc,out} + \dot{m}_{bc,cond}. \quad (5)$$

Due to the low flowing speed of the distillate across the tube, the model assumes that when the distillate leaves the condenser it has the tube surface temperature. The transfer of this sensible heat is calculated according to:

$$\dot{Q}_{bc,w2} = \dot{m}_{bc,cond}h_{bc,ff} + \dot{m}_{bc,in}h_{bc,in} - \dot{m}_{bc,out}h_{bc,w}. \quad (6)$$

The total heat flow rate transferred to the wall tube is the sum of the contributions related to the latent and the sensible heat.

3.1.3. Falling film evaporator

In a falling film evaporator the liquid is sprayed over the first row of the tube bundle. Over the surface of these tubes a thin film of liquid is formed and it falls over the tubes below. The tube surface is at higher temperature than the saturation temperature, therefore, part of the film evaporates. The mass and heat transfer rates are determined by the film thickness, but it changes with the tangential direction of the tube and with the position of the tube in the column. An analytical solution for this problem is more complex than needed. There are many factors which affect the thickness and this is the reason why several authors have published Nusselt number correlations for falling films evaporators [28]. Among them, Sernas [29] and Rogers et al. [30] propose Eq. 7 for horizontal tube bundles with different values for the coefficients. This correlation with coefficients adjusted with real data of the plant is used in this model.

$$Nu_e = n_1 Re_e^{n_2} Pr_e Ar_e^{n_3}. \quad (7)$$

The evaporator model (v. Fig. 5(c)) used in this work was presented in [1]. It is an algebraic lumped model where an average film thickness and average thermodynamic properties for the whole tube bundle are assumed and where the stucle mass effect is neglected.

The mass and energy balances are:

$$0 = \dot{m}_{e,in} - \dot{m}_{e,out} - \dot{m}_{e,ev}, \quad (8)$$

$$0 = \dot{Q}_{e,w} + \dot{m}_{e,in}h_{e,in} - \dot{m}_{e,out}h_e - \dot{m}_{e,ev}h_{e,sv}. \quad (9)$$

The evaporated mass flow rate is:

$$\dot{m}_{e,ev} = \frac{\max(0, \dot{Q}_{e,w} + \dot{m}_{e,in}(h_{e,in} - h_{e,sl}))}{h_{e,sv} - h_{e,sl}}. \quad (10)$$

The outlet mass fraction is:

$$S_{e,out} = \frac{\dot{m}_{e,in}S_{e,in} - \dot{m}_{e,ev}}{\dot{m}_{e,in} - \dot{m}_{e,ev}}. \quad (11)$$

The heat flow rate is:

$$\dot{Q}_{e,w} = N_{e,col}N_{e,row}\bar{\alpha}_eA_e(T_{e,sl} - T_{e,w}). \quad (12)$$

The definition of Nusselt number allows to calculate the average heat transfer coefficient:

$$Nu_e = \left(\frac{\bar{\alpha}_e}{k_e}\right) \left(\frac{v_e^2}{g}\right)^{1/3}. \quad (13)$$

3.1.4. Pipe

The heat transfer to the liquid flowing through a tube is a phenomenon thoroughly studied. Several Modelica libraries includes pipe models that has been tested with good results like Modelica.Fluid [21] or the MMBs library [31]. Nonetheless, the computational effort that entails to connect fourteen pipe models in series has forced to developed a new pipe model simplifying the previous models. The new model (v. Fig. 5(d)) is a lumped model with one CV.

The proposed balances of mass and energy:

$$0 = \dot{m}_{pp,in} - \dot{m}_{pp,out}, \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\rho_{pp,av}V_{pp}}{2} (\dot{h}_{pp,in} + \dot{h}_{pp,out}) = \dot{Q}_{pp,w} + \dot{m}_{pp,in}h_{pp,in} - \dot{m}_{pp,out}h_{pp,out}. \quad (15)$$

All properties of the liquid are evaluated at the average specific enthalpy:

$$h_{pp,av} = \frac{h_{pp,in} + h_{pp,out}}{2}. \quad (16)$$

The heat transfer between the tube surface and the fluid is calculated with the Newton's law of cooling:

$$\dot{Q}_{pp,w} = N_{pp,col}N_{pp,row}\bar{\alpha}_{pp}A_{pp,w}(T_{pp,w} - T_{pp,av}), \quad (17)$$

where the heat transfer coefficient is given by the Dittus-Boelter Nusselt number correlation [32]:

$$Nu_{pp} = 0.023Re_{pp}^{0.8}Pr_{pp}^{0.4}. \quad (18)$$

The Reynolds number is determined considering the number of parallel pipes:

$$Re_{pp} = \frac{4\dot{m}_{pp,in}}{\pi D_{i,pp} \mu_{pp,av} N_{pp,par}}. \quad (19)$$

Besides the first pipe, the inlet specific enthalpy of the fluid in the pipes and its derivative are given by the output of the previous pipe. At the first pipe, the inlet specific enthalpy is one of the inputs of the system, and its derivative needs to be explicitly calculated together with this input. In order to speed up the simulation, this calculation may be performed offline.

3.1.5. Wall

The wall model (v. Fig. 5(e)) is the element that exchanges heat between the inner and outer sides of the tubes. Considering that the thickness of the tube is 0.7 mm and the 90-10 Cu-Ni alloy has a high thermal conductivity, the conduction across the tube can be neglected. A single wall temperature for the whole tube bundle is assumed:

$$\dot{Q}_{ff,w} - \dot{Q}_{pp,w} = m_w C_{p,w} \dot{T}_w. \quad (20)$$

3.1.6. Flash

Flash evaporation is the partial or total vaporization that occurs when liquid gets inside a vessel where the pressure is lower than its saturation pressure. The liquid suddenly evaporates until both pressures are the same. The released latent heat is used to reduce the temperature of the liquid. This process usually happens when seawater flows from one effect to the next, or when the distillate reaches the condenser.

The flash model (v. Fig. 5(f)), also presented in [1], was developed using a single CV without mass or energy storage and where the latent heat from evaporation is used to cool the seawater down until the saturation temperature is reached.

The evaporated mass flow rate is determined by:

$$\dot{m}_{fl,ev} = \frac{\max(0, \dot{m}_{in}(h_{fl,in} - h_{fl,sl}))}{h_{fl,sv} - h_{fl,sl}}. \quad (21)$$

Where the energy and mass balances are:

$$0 = \dot{m}_{fl,in} - \dot{m}_{fl,out} - \dot{m}_{fl,ev}, \quad (22)$$

$$0 = \dot{m}_{fl,in} h_{fl,in} - \dot{m}_{fl,out} h_{fl,out} - \dot{m}_{fl,ev} h_{fl,sv}. \quad (23)$$

If the liquid is seawater, the outlet mass fraction is obtained from an expression similar to Eq. 11.

3.1.7. Gas volume

The vapor generated at the effect fills all the volumen available inside the cell. The gas pressure is required by all the processes that happen in the cell.

This model, based on the model presented in [1], assumes a homogeneous distribution of the vapor inside the cell. The volume is assumed constant because the liquid phase volume of the cell is negligible if it is compared with the gaseous phase volume. The pressure is calculate with the ideal gas law:

$$p_g V_g = m_g K T_g. \quad (24)$$

The temperature of the gas is the saturation temperature of the water at this pressure. This bond between the temperature and the pressure causes an algebraic loop that is efficiently solved by the simulation environment.

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4 The mass is determined by the following mass balance:
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$$\dot{m}_g = \dot{m}_{g,in} - \dot{m}_{g,out}. \quad (25)$$

7 8 9 3.1.8. Mixer

10 The mixer is the element that divides the flow from the extractions of distillate at the 7th, 10th and
11 13th cells. As the model presented in [14], the distillate is proportionally divided.
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$$0 = \dot{m}_{mix,in} - y\dot{m}_{mix,out1} - (1 - y)\dot{m}_{mix,out2}. \quad (26)$$

13 14 15 16 3.1.9. Valve

17 The seawater at the outlet of the condenser is divided by a mass-flow-rate-controlled valve. The
18 feed seawater mass flow rate is provided as input and the valve model determines the cooling seawater
19 rejected.
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22 3.2. Medium level

23 3.2.1. Heater

24 The heater model, depicted as a compact model in Fig. 6(a), wraps the main physical phenomenon that
25 takes place on the 1st effect or heater. These phenomena have been described in §3.1. The arrangement
26 of the model is shown in Fig. 7(a). This model is composed by a pipe, a wall, an evaporator and a flash
27 submodels connected together. In order to consider the heat losses to the environment, the wall model
28 can be connected from the outside by means of the heat transfer connector Q_{env} . The hot water line
29 crosses the heater model from the hw_in to the hw_out fluid connectors releasing its sensible heat from
30 the pipe model to the wall model. The wall model transfers this heat to the falling film evaporator model.
31 The seawater line goes into the heater from the sw_in connector, and leaves it, after crossing the flash
32 and evaporator models, by the sw_out connector. The vapor produced at flash and evaporator models is
33 collected in the v_out connector.
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39 3.2.2. Effect

40 In a similar way to the heater model, the effect model is also composed by the submodels presented
41 in §3.1. Fig. 6(b) wraps the arrangement shown in Fig. 7(b). The seawater line, just as in the heater
42 model, crosses the effect from the sw_in connector to the sw_out connector going through of the flash
43 and evaporator models. The vapor generated in these submodels is collected by the v_out connector.
44 The heat source in this case is the horizontal tube bundle condenser which transfers the sensible heat
45 of the incoming distillate (dis_in) and the latent heat of the vapor coming from the previous cell (v_in).
46 The distillate produced in the condenser leaves the effect through the dis_out connector. The heat is
47 exchanged between the condenser and the evaporator by means of the wall submodel.
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51 3.2.3. Preheater

52 The preheater model, Fig. 6(c), constructed as shown in Fig. 7(c), allows heat transfer between a
53 vapor volume, which condenses outside of a tube bundle, and a seawater flow. The gas volume model
54 manages the vapor of the cell. The vapor enters from the v_in connector and leaks in the v_out connector.
55 Part of the vapor is consumed by the falling film condenser producing distillate that leaves the preheater
56 though the dis_out connector and heat that is transferred to the pipe model through the wall model. The
57 seawater line goes into the preheater model from the sw_in connector and leaves it though the sw_out
58 connector after being heated in the pipe model.
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3.2.4. Condenser

The final condenser behaves like a big preheater where all the distillate produced in the plant is collected. The model (v. Fig. 6(d)) is constructed as Fig. 7(d) shows. All the distillate of the plant enters the condenser through the *dis_in* connector. A flash model divides the flow, part is evaporated and goes to the gas model, and part is added to the distillate produced by the falling film condenser which is collected in the *dis_out* connector. The *v_in* connector provides the vapor coming from the effect. The falling film condenser releases the latent heat of the vapor which is transferred through the wall model to the seawater line by means of the pipe model. This line goes into the condenser from the *sw_in* connector to the *sw_out* connector. The derivative of the inlet specific enthalpy can be provided by the *dsw* connector.

3.3. High level

The final arrangement of the model is depicted in Fig. 8. The connections of the submodels have been performed as shown in Fig. 4. The model is fed at 14th cell by a fluid source which provides the seawater with a constant salinity of $S=0.003326$, and, mass flow rate and temperature obtained from experimental data. The three-way valve divides the seawater flow at the exit of the final condenser where part is rejected and goes to the pool and the remaining part is used to feed the plant. This split is controlled by the feed seawater mass flow rate signal. A fluid source provides the heater with hot water whose mass flow rate and temperature are experimentally obtained. A convection model calculates the heat losses of the plant to the environment. The derivative of the inlet specific enthalpy of the hot water and seawater inputs are provided in order to improve the efficiency of the model. Three sink models are used to establish the outlet boundary conditions.

4. Simulation

Dymola 2015 [33] was the Modelica tool used for the simulation of the mathematical models previously introduced in §3. The numerical solver used was DASSL [34] where the absolute and relative tolerance was set to 10^{-4} . A common laptop, Intel i5 hyper-threading dual-core processor with 8 Gbytes of RAM, was the machine used for the simulations.

The experimental measures used as inputs in the simulations were (v. Fig. 4):

- Inlet hot water mass flow rate (F_{h1})
- Inlet hot water temperature ($Th0$)
- Inlet feed seawater mass flow rate (F_{f0})
- Inlet feed and cooling seawater mass flow rate (F_{c0})
- Inlet feed and cooling seawater temperature (T_{c0})
- Ambient temperature (T_{amb})

The derivatives of the specific enthalpy of the hot water and seawater were numerically estimated by the first order backward difference formula.

Although every variable calculated in the model can be considered as an output, the most relevant are the following:

- Outlet hot water temperature ($Th1$)

- Outlet distillate mass flow rate ($Fd0$)
- Outlet condenser seawater temperature ($Tf0$)
- Pressure at the final condenser ($P14$)

The calibration and validation were accomplished with data from the experiments performed the 14th and 18th October 2013 respectively. In these experiments, the plant was only operated in the solar mode and the inputs were varied over all the operation range. The measured data were filtered by a low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ Hz in order to reduce the noise in the signals. The calibration was carried out by parts (heater, effect, preheater, condenser and MED models) using the Modelica Optimization library [35].

The model has 57 continuous time states (cts): the wall temperature of heater, effects, preheaters and condenser (28 cts), the mass of the gas volume of preheaters and condenser (14 cts), the outlet specific enthalpy of the pipe of preheaters and condenser (14 cts), and the outlet specific enthalpy of the pipe of heater (1 cts). All of them must be correctly initialized. A completely initialization in steady-state initial conditions in practice is not possible because the model requires to start the simulation with non-zero mass flow rates and the state equations are entanglement. The following guideline has been used for the initialization: the wall temperatures have been initialized in steady-state conditions ($\dot{T}_w = 0$), the gas volume masses have been initialized according to a lineal arrangement of pressures between the 1st and the 14th cells using the experimental measures ($P1-P14$) as references, the outlet specific enthalpy of seawater at the preheaters are initialized according to a lineal arrangement of temperatures between the 1st and the 13th cells using experimental measures ($Tf-Tf1$), the outlet specific enthalpy of seawater at the final condenser is initialized according to the measured temperature ($Tf0$) and the outlet specific enthalpy of the hot water at the heater is initialized according to the measured temperature ($Th1$).

The CPU-time for integration was 10.8 s for the 17000 s simulated. The simulation did not present state events and the maximum order of integration used by the numerical integrator 3.

Fig. 9 and 10 show the simulation results of the validation day. The simulation begins when the experimental plant operation has been started, and the hot water and feed and cooling seawater have non-zero mass flow rates at both inputs. Along the experiment, their values change several times abruptly covering almost all the operation range of the plant, as it is shown in Fig. 9(a). For the same reason, the inlet hot water temperature also changes several times (v. Fig. 9(b)). The remaining inputs, the ambient temperature and the inlet seawater temperature, are uncontrolled variables and may change with time. The variation of them is shown at Fig. 9(c).

At the beginning of the simulation, it can be observed small spikes in the model response with respect to the measured variables. The cause of them is a small difference between the proposed initial values of the continuous time states and the real values. Outlet hot water and outlet condenser seawater temperatures show good agreements with respect to experimental data (cf. Fig. 9(b) and 9(c)). Although the absolute error exceeds the uncertainty range of the measurement instruments in certain occasions, 0.85 °C, the average error reveals the goodness of fit obtained with the model since it is lower than the uncertainty range, 0.65 and 0.81 °C respectively. The distillate mass flow rate and the pressure of the condenser show higher deviations with respect to experimental data. Nevertheless, the uncertainty range at these two measures is barely higher than the measured value. The average absolute error are 0.0458 kg/s and 8.0 mbar respectively.

5. Conclusions

A new dynamic model of a solar-assisted MED plant has been developed. It is based on physical principles and using object-oriented modeling methodology, the non-linear model predicts the thermal behavior of the plant. The main subprocesses that take place at the plant have been identified and modeled. Each one of them has been modeled in a self-sufficient component making up a library of submodels. Three levels of detail have been enough to develop the model: the low level is used to cover each subprocess of heat and mass transfer of the system, the medium level is used to assemble subsystems, and the high level is used to compose the complete model of the plant. The MED model uses as inputs the natural inputs of the system, i.e., the hot water flow, the inlet seawater flow and the ambient temperature. The model has been developed using the object-oriented Modelica language and it has been calibrated and successfully validated against experimental data from the PSA solar thermal desalination plant. A good agreement between simulation results and experimental data is obtained where the simulation average error is lower than the uncertainty range of the measurement instruments.

The model covers the whole operation range of the plant and it can be used to study the plant performance in different scenarios and operating strategies to optimize future operating control strategies. The assumptions considered allows fast simulation useful for testing control algorithms. To develop a control system to optimize the energy consumption of the plant is one of the short-term aims. Another goal is to improve the response of the model with new assumptions which do not penalize the computational time.

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References

- [1] A. de la Calle, J. Bonilla, L. Roca, P. Palenzuela, Dynamic modeling and performance of the first cell of a multi-effect distillation plant, *Appl Therm Eng* 70 (2014) 410–420.
- [2] S. Kalogirou, Seawater desalination using renewable energy sources, *Prog Energy Combust* 31 (2005) 242–281.
- [3] C. Li, Y. Goswami, E. Stefanakos, Solar assisted sea water desalination: A review, *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 19 (2013) 136–163.
- [4] M. T. Ali, H. E. Fath, P. R. Armstrong, A comprehensive techno-economical review of indirect solar desalination, *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 15 (2011) 4187–4199.
- [5] H. M. Qiblawey, F. Banat, Solar thermal desalination technologies, *Desalination* 220 (2008) 633–644.
- [6] R. Kouhikamali, Thermodynamic analysis of feed water pre-heaters in multiple effect distillation systems, *Appl Therm Eng* 50 (2013) 1157–1163.

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4 [7] H.-J. Joo, H.-Y. Kwak, Performance evaluation of multi-effect distiller for optimized solar thermal
5 desalination, *Appl Therm Eng* 61 (2013) 491–499.
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7
8 [8] P. Palenzuela, G. Zaragoza, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, J. Blanco, Evaluation of cooling technologies of
9 concentrated solar power plants and their combination with desalination in the mediterranean area,
10 *Appl Therm Eng* 50 (2013) 1514–1521.
11
12 [9] A. M. El-Nashar, Predicting part load performance of small MED evaporators-a simple simulation
13 program and its experimental verification, *Desalination* 130 (2000) 217–234.
14
15 [10] A. M. El-Nashar, Validating the performance simulation program “SOLDES” using data from an
16 operating solar desalination plant, *Desalination* 130 (2000) 235–253.
17
18 [11] P. Palenzuela, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, G. Zaragoza, J. Blanco-Gálvez, M. Ibarra, Parametric equa-
19 tions for the variables of a steady-state model of a multi-effect desalination plant, *Desalin Water*
20 *Treat* 51 (2013) 1229–1241.
21
22 [12] G. Kishore, S. Nisan, S. Dardou, A. K. Adak, V. K. Srivastava, P. K. Tewari, Development of a
23 dynamic simulator (INFMED) for the MED/VC plant, *Desalin Water Treat* 21 (2010) 364–374.
24
25 [13] L. Roca, L. J. Yebra, M. Berenguel, A. de la Calle, Dynamic modeling and simulation of a multi-
26 effect distillation plant, in: *Proc. 9th International Modelica Conference, Munich, Germany, 2012*,
27 pp. 883–888.
28
29 [14] P. Palenzuela, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, J. Blanco-Gálvez, E. Guillén, M. Ibarra, G. Zaragoza, Model-
30 ing of the heat transfer of a solar multi-effect distillation plant at the Plataforma Solar de Almería,
31 *Desalin Water Treat* 31 (2011) 257–268.
32
33 [15] L. Roca, L. J. Yebra, M. Berenguel, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, Modeling of a Solar Seawater Desalina-
34 tion Plant for Automatic Operation Purposes, *J Sol Energy Eng* 130 (2008) 041009–1–041009–8.
35
36 [16] Y.-D. Kim, K. Thu, A. Myat, K. C. Ng, Numerical simulation of solar-assisted multi-effect distilla-
37 tion (SMED) desalination systems, *Desalin Water Treat* 51 (2013) 1242–1253.
38
39 [17] K. Thu, Y.-D. Kim, G. Amy, W. G. Chun, K. C. Ng, A synergetic hybridization of adsorption cycle
40 with the multi-effect distillation (MED), *Appl Therm Eng* 62 (2014) 245–255.
41
42 [18] D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, J. Blanco-Gálvez, L. García-Rodríguez, W. Gernjak, S. Malato, First exper-
43 imental results of a new hybrid solar/gas multi-effect distillation system: the AQUASOL project,
44 *Desalination* 220 (2008) 619–625.
45
46 [19] P. Palenzuela, L. Roca, G. Zaragoza, D. Alarcón-Padilla, L. García, A. de la Calle, Operational
47 improvements to increase the efficiency of an absorption heat pump connected to a Multi-Effect
48 Distillation unit, *Appl Therm Eng* 63 (2014) 84–96.
49
50 [20] P. Fernández-Izquierdo, L. García-Rodríguez, D. C. Alarcón-Padilla, P. Palenzuela, I. Martín-
51 Mateos, Experimental analysis of a multi-effect distillation unit operated out of nominal conditions,
52 *Desalination* 284 (2012) 233–237.
53
54 [21] Modelica Association, Modelica Specification 3.3, 2014. URL: www.modelica.org/documents.
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[22] M. Kunick, H.-J. Kretzschmar, U. Gampe, Fast Calculation of Thermodynamic Properties of Water and Steam in Process Modelling using Spline Interpolation, in: Proc. ICPWS XV, Berlin, Germany, 2008, p. 5.

[23] IAPWS, Release on the IAPWS, Industrial Formulation 1997 for the Thermodynamic Properties of Water and Steam, Technical Report, Erlangen, Germany, 1997. URL: www.iapws.org/relguide/IF97-Rev.pdf.

[24] M. Sharqawy, Thermophysical properties of seawater: A review of existing correlations and data, *Desalin Water Treat* 16 (2010) 354–380.

[25] V. Dhir, J. Lienhard, Laminar Film Condensation on Plane and Axisymmetric Bodies in Nonuniform Gravity, *J Heat Trans* 1 (1971) 97–100.

[26] F. P. Incropera, T. L. Bergman, D. P. DeWitt, A. S. Lavine, Principles of heat and mass transfer, 7 ed., John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, 2012.

[27] J. C. Chato, Laminar condensation inside horizontal and inclined tubes, *ASHRAE J* 4 (1962) 52–60.

[28] J. Fernández-Seara, A. A. Pardiñas, Refrigerant falling film evaporation review: Description, fluid dynamics and heat transfer, *Appl Therm Eng* 64 (2014) 155–171.

[29] V. Sernas, Heat transfer correlation for subcooled water films on horizontal tubes, *J Heat Trans* 101 (1979) 176–178.

[30] J. Rogers, S. Goindi, M. Lamari, Turbulent falling film flow and heat transfer on horizontal tube, in: Proc. of the National Heat Transfer Conference, Portland, 1995, pp. 3–12.

[31] J. Bonilla, S. Dormido, F. E. Cellier, Switching moving boundary models for two-phase flow evaporators and condensers, *Commun Nonlinear Sci Numer Sim* (2014).

[32] F. W. Dittus, L. M. K. Boelter, Heat transfer in automobile radiators of the tubular Type, *Int Commun Heat Mass Transf* 12 (1985) 3–22.

[33] Dassault Systemes, Dymola 2015 - Dynamic Modeling Laboratory, 2014. URL: www.3ds.com.

[34] L. R. Petzold, A description of DASSL: a Differential/Algebraic System Solver, *Scientific Computing* (1983) 65–68.

[35] A. Pfeiffer, Optimization Library for Interactive Multi-Criteria Optimization Tasks, in: Proc. 9th International Modelica Conference, Munich, Germany, 2012, pp. 669–680.

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Nomenclature

A	Area (m^2)	ν	Kinematic viscosity ($m^2 \cdot s^{-1}$)
Ar	Archimedes number (dimensionless)	ρ	Density ($kg \cdot m^{-3}$)
C_p	Specific heat capacity at constant pressure ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	<i>Subscripts</i>	
D_i	Internal diameter (m)	av	Average
F	Apparent wet area fraction (dimensionless)	bc	Horizontal tube bundle condenser
g	Gravitational acceleration ($m \cdot s^{-2}$)	c	Falling film condenser
H	Enthalpy (J)	col	Column
h	Specific enthalpy ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)	cond	Condensate
L	Latent heat of vaporization ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)	e	Falling film evaporator
m	Mass (kg)	ev	Evaporated
N	Number (dimensionless)	ff	Falling film evaporator or condenser
Nu	Nusselt number (dimensionless)	fl	Flash
n	Nusselt correlation coefficient (dimensionless)	fs	Feed seawater
K	Mass gas constant ($J \cdot K^{-1} \cdot kg^{-1}$)	g	Gas volume
k	Thermal conductivity ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	hw	Hot water
Pr	Prandtl number (dimensionless)	in	Inlet
p	Pressure (Pa)	mea	Measured
Q	Heat (J)	mix	Mixer
Re	Reynolds number (dimensionless)	out	Outlet
r	Radius (m)	p	Pressure flow
S	Salinity, salt mass fraction (dimensionless)	par	Parallel pipes
T	Temperature (K)	pp	Pipe
V	Volume (m^3)	row	Row
y	Proportional number (dimensionless)	sim	Simulated
<i>Greek symbols</i>		sl	Saturated liquid
α	Heat transfer coefficient ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$)	sv	Saturated vapor
μ	Dynamic viscosity ($kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-1}$)	w & w2	Pipe wall
		water	Water

Newton's notation is used for time derivatives.

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Table 1: Design specification of PSA-MED plant [11]

Number of effects	14
Heat source energy consumption	200 kW
Performance ratio	>9
Hot water flow rate	12 L/s
Feed seawater flow rate	8 m ³ /h
Brine reject	5 m ³ /h
Distillate production	3 m ³ /h
Top brine temperature	68°C
Condenser temperature	33°C
Vacuum system	Hydroejectors (seawater at 3bar)

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Figure 1: AQUASOL project plant flow sheet

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Figure 2: MED plant at PSA

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Figure 3: Cross-sectional view of a cell

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Figure 4: Schematic diagram of the MED plant at PSA

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Figure 5: Low level models

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(a) Heater

(b) Effect

(c) Preheater

(d) Condenser

Figure 6: Medium level models

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(a) Heater

(b) Effect

(c) Preheater

(d) Condenser

Figure 7: Medium level encapsulations

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Figure 8: High Level Model

(a) Inlet mass flow rates

(b) Inlet and outlet hot water temperatures

(c) Inlet and outlet feed and cooling seawater temperatures

Figure 9: Inlets and outlets of the model

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(a) Distillate mass flow rate

(b) Final condenser pressure

Figure 10: Inlets and outlets of the model II

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